

A State of the Art of Drowning Death Detection and Prevention Systems with Various Communication Technologies and Discussion on their Performance

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Abstract

Drowning is most terrifying accident to most of the children and adult which prevent them from using swimming pools for recreation and fitness .The present article focuses on accuracy in drown predict ,notify and saving inventions .Comparison and short falls in research work done so far done .Research gaps were identified in available art work and proposed improvements .This review article focused mainly of drown safety related inventions and research articles in databases .The present study thrown light on how many technologies were being used to predict and avoid drown deaths .

Keywords: *Swimming Pool, Image Processing, Image Processing Technique, Drowning Accident, Drowning Detection System, Drowning Prevention System, Waterside Monitoring System, Drowning Detection, Portable Bather Monitoring Device, Complex Image Processing Technique, Motion Responsive Swimming Pool, Drowning Victim, Responsive Swimming Pool Safety.*

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